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Electromagnetic and mechanical design of the two guns

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ABSTRACT

Work Package 7.4 aims to design, construct, and test two very high gradient (up to 200 MV/m on the cathode) C-band (5.712 GHz) electron RF Guns. The first of these RF guns is a Standing-Wave (SW) with 2.5 accelerating cells and the second a many-celled traveling-wave (TW) structure incorporating the photocathode in the very first cell. The present Milestone reports on the details of the electromagnetic and mechanical design of the two guns.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	4
2	STANDING WAVE GUN	7
2.1	ELECTROMAGNETIC DESIGN	7
2.2	MECHANICAL DESIGN	10
3	TRAVELLING WAVE GUN.....	13
3.1	ELECTROMAGNETIC DESIGN	13
3.2	MECHANICAL DESIGN.....	16
4	FUTURE PLANS AND CONCLUSION.....	17
5	REFERENCES.....	18

Executive summary

In the Report, we summarize the activities related to the electromagnetic and mechanical design of the two radiofrequency (rf) photo-guns, one a Standing Wave (SW) design and the other a Traveling Wave (TW) gun, that are now being developed in the framework of the Task 7.4. Both devices operate in the C-band (5.712 GHz) regime and have been designed to reach a cathode peak field above the 160 MV/m. After a short introduction on the state of the art of photo-gun and their operation, the design of the two guns is illustrated in two dedicated chapters. The SW gun is a 2.5 cells gun fed by a four-port mode launcher, on axis. The overall design has been oriented to reduce the main quantities that allow to keep under control the breakdown rate such as the surface peak electric field, the rf pulse length and the modified Poynting vector. A particular effort has been put on the design of the cooling system that allows to operate the gun at repetition frequencies larger than 400 Hz. The mechanical design has been oriented towards a brazing free realization of the device, and in particular of the accelerating cells, with the use of the special gasket technology recently developed at INFN. The TW gun is a unique 12-cell gun fed by an on-axis coaxial waveguide. The design focused on the ease of fabrication, due to a more complex RF design than SW guns, and maximising the ratio of the on-axis cathode electric field to the peak electric field in the remainder of the structure. The design will be constructed using SwissFEL brazing technology that has demonstrated excellent reliability for high gradient applications. The short RF pulse length requirements (100 ns) means that repetition rates in excess of 400 Hz are feasible. Finally, the TW gun features a load-lock capability for fast cathode exchange under vacuum.

1 Introduction

Task 7.4 is related to the design, fabrication, and test of two new radiofrequency (rf) photo-guns operating in the C-band (5.712 GHz) frequency band. Photo-guns are widely used in modern particle accelerator facilities, particularly in FELs, as they provide very low-emittance, high-brightness electron bunches. The basic principle of an RF gun is an RF cavity that has a cathode embedded in the structure from which electrons can be extracted. An external RF power source excites the cavity's accelerating mode so that with the introduction of a laser pulse on the cathode, at a short enough wavelength, photo-electrons are emitted. Careful adjustment of the phase allows for immediate acceleration of the electron bunch by the rf electric field on the cathode and continual acceleration all along the gun beam axis. The operation of this type of devices is schematically represented in Fig. 1. Under the combined action of the RF accelerating field and of an external solenoidal magnetic field, the dynamics of the electron beam are guided and controlled, and low-emittance, high-brightness bunches are produced and injected in the accelerating structures placed downstream. Presently, the RF technology mostly used for RF Guns is the S-band (3 GHz) frequency regime or lower. S-band is used, in particular, for facilities operating at low pulse repetition rates ($f_{\text{rep}} \leq 120$ Hz). According to beam dynamics studies, the higher the peak electric field on the cathode, the better the quality of the beam emerging from the gun. In this respect, S-band rf guns represents the state-of-the-art, providing typical peak fields of 100-120 MV/m on the cathode. Larger values would be very much desirable, to further improve the beam quality. However, it was found experimentally that going beyond 120 MV/m in S-band based injectors was very difficult and led to an unreliable electron source. The

limitation comes from the unacceptable increase in the RF breakdown rate (BDR). RF Breakdown is a complex phenomenon that depends on many aspects, including the RF pulse parameters, conditioning time and strategy, construction quality, surface cleanliness, residual pressure. The C-band frequency regime (5.712 GHz) is a more recent technology whose reliability and effectiveness have been already fully demonstrated. Successful FEL radiation facilities such as SwissFEL in Switzerland and SACLA in Japan are based on linacs made of travelling-wave C-band accelerating sections. The technology is also industrially mature, since power sources and the needed ancillary components (driver amplifiers, waveguides, ceramic windows, dummy loads, LLRFs, isolators and pulse compressors) are all available on the market. However, beam injectors fully based on this technology are yet to be developed. There are solid reasons to believe that the frequency step-up from S-band to C-band can provide an improvement of the photo-injector beam quality. This is mainly related to the filling time reduction in case of Standing wave cavities, corresponding to an rf pulse duration shortening, which scales as $f^{3/2}$, and to the increase in the RF structure efficiency (the shunt impedance per unit length) which scales as $f^{1/2}$. These allow a saving of RF power to reach the design peak electric field. In the case of rf TW Gun the filling time is already shorter compared to SW gun due to intrinsic large bandwidth and scales as f^{-1} while the required RF power is almost independent from the number of cells since the larger part of the RF power is dissipated in the rf load. This allows a higher beam mean energy at the rf gun output. Because of its higher efficiency, a C-band RF Gun is also suitable for application requiring repetition rates in the 100 Hz ÷ 1 kHz range.

Fig. 1: sketch of the operational of a photo-gun.

In the framework of the Task 7.4, two different photo-guns will be optimized, built, tested and compared, namely a SW over-coupled cavity made of two-and-a-half cells and a multi-cell TW accelerating section incorporating a photocathode in the very first cell. Both approaches are attractive, with different advantages to be exploited, and deserve to be fully experimentally explored.

The availability of a new state-of-the-art, compact and cost-effective electron injector would bring benefits to a large accelerator user community, primarily to the facilities at the frontiers of the beam quality such as FEL radiation sources, Thomson/Compton photon sources and plasma-based accelerators requiring external injection of the beam. Upgrades of existing machines and new projects based on normal-conducting RF and oriented to higher repetition rates to increase average beam current and fluxes of physics events would also greatly appreciate this development. Compact dimensions, high flux and cost effectiveness expand the potential of these devices towards industrial applications and small-scale research facilities.

2 Standing Wave Gun

2.1 ELECTROMAGNETIC DESIGN

The standing wave (SW) gun is a 2.5-cell copper structure coupled through a mode launcher to the feeding rectangular waveguide WR187 connected to the radiofrequency source (klystron). It operates at 5.712 GHz and, according to the high gradient test performed on X-band structures and according to the scaling laws that allow to keep under control the breakdown rate (BDR) [1], its electromagnetic (e.m.) design has been optimized to minimize the peak surface electric field normalized to the cathode field (E_{surf}/E_{cath}), the modified Poynting vector (S_c), the radiofrequency (rf) pulse length (t_p) and pulsed heating (ΔT_{pulsed}) [2]. To this purpose, the gun has been designed with a coupling coefficient equal to 3 to allow operation with short rf pulses ($t_p=300$ ns) thus reducing the BDR, the pulsed heating and the power dissipation. An elliptical profile of the irises between the accelerating cells has been also implemented to reduce the peak surface electric field. The irises have a relatively large aperture to increase the frequency separation with respect to the nearest $\pi/2$ -mode thus avoiding excitation of this mode when the structure is fed with short rf pulses. The large iris apertures also allow a better pumping of the cathode cell. A four-port mode launcher [3, 4] with an on-axis coupling has been also adopted to reduce the pulsed heating on the coupler and to have a perfect compensation of the dipole and quadrupole field components induced by the coupler itself. The mode launcher has been also designed to integrate two pumping ports. The e.m. design has been done with ANSYS [5] and the e.m. model is reported in Fig. 2 with the magnitude of the electric field. The final gun parameters are given in Table I.

Fig. 2: electromagnetic model of the gun.

Table I: Main Parameters of the C-band Gun (in parenthesis there are those referred to the 400 Hz case)

Parameter	value
Resonant frequency	5.712
$E_{\text{cath}}/\sqrt{P_{\text{diss}}}$ [MV/(m·MW ^{0.5})]	51.4
rf input power [MW]	18
Cathode peak field [MV/m]	160
Rep. rate [Hz]	100 (400)
Quality factor	11900
Filling time [ns]	166
Coupling coefficient	3
rf pulse length (t_p) [ns]	300
Mode sep. π - $\pi/2$ [MHz]	47
$E_{\text{surf}}/E_{\text{cath}}$	0.96
Mod. Poy. vector [W/ μm^2]	2.5
Pulsed heating [°C]	16
Average diss. Power [W]	250 (1000)

The gun main dimensions and the magnitude and phase of the longitudinal electric field on axis are reported in Figures 3 and 4 respectively. This last plot put in evidence that the accelerating field is a perfect standing wave in the accelerating cells while, in the coupler region, it has a residual travelling wave component (non-constant phase) related to the power flow from the input coupler circular waveguide into the structure. The effect of these travelling wave components on the beam dynamics has been carefully studied also in the case of long circular waveguides [6] and does not affect the beam dynamics.

Fig. 3: gun main dimensions.

Fig. 4: longitudinal electric field on axis.

The magnitude of the magnetic field on three different arcs, with radius 5 mm, in the mode launcher region, is reported in Fig. 5. The arcs are in the center of the mode launcher itself (corresponding to the $z=100$ mm longitudinal position of Fig. 4), in the center of the circular waveguide ($z=80$ mm) and at the beginning of the output beam pipe ($z=120$ mm).

Fig. 5: magnetic field on three arcs ($r=5$ mm) in the mode launcher region.

The plot put in evidence that the residual quadrupole component is completely negligible while there is an octupole component that vanishes moving toward the circular waveguide. Moreover, for a given arc, it is possible to verify that the phase of the field is constant and, for this reason, it is possible to perform a spatial Fourier analysis, according to the formula [7]:

$$B_{\theta}(r, \vartheta, z) \cong A_0(z)r + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(z)e^{j\varphi_n(z)} \cos(n\vartheta) r^{n-1}$$

where the A_n terms are the magnitude of the multipole components. The quadrupole component is that associated to the term with $n=2$ while the octupole to the term $n=4$. Their values, in the center of the coupler, are $3.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ T/m and 400 T/m³ respectively at the nominal cathode peak field of 160 MV/m. Beam dynamics simulations, considering also the effect of these multipole components, have shown that their effects on the beam parameters are completely negligible.

2.2 MECHANICAL DESIGN

The gun will be realized with the new brazing-free technology developed at INFN-LNF [8] and already adopted for the realization of new rf photo-guns [9,10]. This technology has been demonstrated to exhibit very good performances in term of BDR and conditioning time, with a contemporary reduction of the cost and realization time. The gun has been completely designed and is now in the realization phase. The 3D mechanical layout is given in Fig. 6(a). In the figure there are also reported the other components to operate the gun such as the pumping system, the solenoid and the laser injection chamber. All the components have been designed and are now under realizations. Fig. 7 schematically sketches the assembly procedure with gaskets while Fig. 6(b) report the assembly mechanical drawing of the gun with the different cells and components now under fabrication.

Fig. 6: (a) 3D mechanical layout of the SW gun and components; (b) assembly mechanical drawing of the SW gun

Fig. 7: mechanical drawing showing the assembly procedure of the SW gun.

The operation at 100 Hz with 300 ns rf pulses results in an average dissipated power into the gun body of 250 W. The gun has been designed also to operate with a higher repetition rate compatible, for example, with the 400 Hz operation now under consideration for the EUPRAXIA@SPARC_LAB

project [9]. In this case the dissipated power in the gun is ~ 1 kW. For this reason, a careful design of the cooling system has been performed to avoid detuning of the gun during operation, and not uniform deformations with a consequence unbalance of the accelerating field in the cells [12]. The gun integrates four cooling channels, as given in Fig. 8a: three for the cells (with internal diameter of 7 mm) and one for the cathode (with a square section ~ 100 mm²). In each cooling pipe of the cells it is foreseen a continuous flow of demineralized water of about 2.5 liter/min while for the cathode (because of the larger cooling pipe section) a flow rate of 5 liter/min. The 3D model of the gun, including the cooling system, has been implemented in ANSYS Workbench environment [5] and a full coupled thermal, structural and electromagnetic analysis, has been performed. The heat load obtained by the e.m. analysis has been imported in the thermo-mechanical module, the temperature distribution has been calculated and the mechanical deformations have been then calculated. The water temperature of the cooling pipes in the 400 Hz operation and the final temperature distribution are given in Figs. 8a and 8b and the corresponding deformations are depicted in Fig. 8c. In the calculations we have considered an input water temperature, and corresponding nominal gun temperature, of 22 °C. The deformed structure has then been simulated with the e.m. module and the calculated detuning is of ~ 1 MHz while we verified that the field distribution is not affected. The reflection coefficients at the input port, under powering, are reported in Fig. 9 for the 100 Hz and 400 Hz cases and are compared with the nominal one. The plot clearly shows the resonance frequency variation due to the cavity deformation. This detuning can be either compensated by changing the water temperature during powering or by designing the structure with a resonant frequency higher than the nominal one.

To deeply investigate the gun properties, simulations of the dark current have been also performed [13]. These simulations are important for the radioprotection point of view and high power test stand setup. The calculated charge per period at the laser injection chamber at 160 MV/m with a β enhancement factor of 70 is of 15 fC with a total maximum charge on the rf pulse length well below the 25 pC level.

Fig. 8: gun cooling system (a); (b) temperature (°C) distribution (at 400 Hz) and mechanical deformations (mm)(c).

Fig. 9: reflection coefficient under powering.

3 Travelling Wave Gun

3.1 ELECTROMAGNETIC DESIGN

The design for the Travelling-Wave Radio-Frequency (TW RF) Photogun was loosely based on a previous concept design that was developed as part of a PhD thesis at the Paul Scherrer Institut [14]. This past design features 10 regular cells with two input coupling cells (10+2), one of which houses the photocathode. The cells operate within the C-band frequency regime, specifically at 5.712 GHz, with a phase advance of 120 degrees. All cells have a length matched for a beam travelling at the speed of light except the first cell that is designed for a mean velocity of roughly $0.5c$. The structure is constant impedance. The RF design is illustrated in Figure 10 below. The design can be separated into three sections. The input coupler, the cells and the output coupler, the details of which will be discussed separately below.

Figure 10: The vacuum design of the TW RF Photogun.

During the design evaluation of the past conceptual design, discussed above, it was found that the coupler style would be very complicated to manufacture and operate due to the mechanical connection of the inner conductor. The new input coupler design aimed to keep the coaxial design to reduce multipole components on the cathode. The input coupler begins with a WR187 dual waveguide input that feeds a waveguide to coaxial RF transition. This transition features a coupling cell and a chamfer of the cell wall to the inner conductor. The function of this chamfer is two fold. The first function is to increase in the coupler bandwidth from 53 MHz to 100 MHz. The second function is to remove a local potential well in the electric field. Such regions are prone to multipacting in coaxial waveguides [15]. The input coupler's coaxial waveguide extends a length of 100 mm. The length of this coaxial is dictated primarily by the size constraints of the high field solenoid and bucking coil that are fitted around the structure. Although of consideration in the length of this coaxial is the multipole components, which result from the dual-fed waveguide coupler. At the end of the coaxial

are four magnetic slots that couple the RF power into the input coupling cell. The choice of using magnetic slots rather than an electrically coupled iris, as used in the original concept design, was due to an investigation into the tolerance requirements of the coaxial inner conductor. These studies found that the inner conductor needed to remain within 50 μm of the beam axis. Consequently, it was determined that brazing the inner conductor to the outer conductor was highly desirable. For the photogun it was desirable that the cathode could be exchanged through the use of a load-lock system. To give such a capability, the inner conductor of the input coupler was hollowed allowing the paths for a cathode to be inserted into place. This will be further discussed in the mechanical design section below.

Figure 11: The full mechanical construction of the TW RF Photogun with the simple load-lock system.

For the output coupler, the design evaluation of the coupler style found that the output coupler's inner conductor was much less sensitive to misalignments and therefore it need not be brazed in place. However, these evaluations did find some areas of concern in the conceptual design. The first was the presence of RF chokes and filtering cells that may be prone to multipacting. The conclusion of this evaluation was that these chokes and filters should be removed if possible. Removing these feature meant that the output coupler was no longer dismountable. Without this feature, a new concept to mount the high field solenoid around the gun must be devised. To tackle this, the output coupler was designed such that the WR187 waveguide flange was embedded in the body of the structure rather than at the end of two waveguide arms brazed to the body. This reduced the outer radius of the output coupler in the mechanical design to 70 mm.

For the regular cells, it was decided that the regular cell design and the length of the 'input coupling cell' used in the original conceptual design was appropriate for the new design. The reason to use this design was due to extensive beam dynamics studies on the cell lengths performed prior to this project.

Figure 12: The fieldmap of magnitude of the complex electric and magnetic fields.

The electromagnetic fieldmaps are illustrated in Figure 12. The electric field on the centre of the cathode is 200 MV/m for an input power of 82 MW. Given this input power it is important to understand the surface magnetic fields, in particular around the magnetic coupling slots. We find that the peak magnetic field is 558 kA/m. This value is large; however, given a short RF pulse length of 100 ns, the pulsed surface heating within the structure is limited to 30 K which is below the 50 K commonly quoted as begin the damaged threshold. A comprehensive list of the RF parameters is found in Table 2.

Table 2 The RF parameters of the TW RF Photogun.

Parameter	Value	Units
Frequency	5.712	GHz
No. of Accelerating Cells	10+2	
Cell Length	17.495	mm
Structure Length	250	mm
Phase Advance per Cell	120	degrees
Attenuation	-1.41	dB
Group velocity	0.79	%c
Filling Time	90	ns
Input Power	82	MW
Peak E Field (Irises)	175	MV/m
Peak E field (Cathode centre)	200	MV/m
Peak H Field	558	kA/m
Pulsed surface heating (100 ns)	30.6	K

3.2 MECHANICAL DESIGN

With the completed RF design, the work on the mechanical design was commenced. The first concept to decide upon was how to construct the TW RF Photogun. It was decided that the tuning-free brazed structure concept, which had been used on the SwissFEL, FERMI FEL and a few other high gradient projects, would be used for the TW RF Photogun [16-18]. This was to take advantage of the in-house expertise for fabrication using this method. The concept also has cooling channels integrated into the cell body that allows for efficient power dissipation. We see the dissipative abilities through thermal simulations.

Nominal operation of the RF gun consists of 82 MW, 100 ns RF pulses with pulse repetition rates of at least 100 Hz. This equates to a power dissipation of 227 W for 100 Hz operation and 2.27 kW for 1 kHz operation. Figure 4 illustrates the thermal heating of the structure caused by RF power dissipation. The temperature differential in the entire structure is found to be 2 K and 20 K for 100 Hz and 1 kHz operation, respectively. The only cell that has a large temperature differential is the input coupling cell where the heating occurs on the cathode that is more thermally isolated. It will be important that the spring holding the cathode in place has a good thermal and electrical contact to prevent overheating. If the expansion of this cathode due to heating does lead to an increase in the S11 the cathode position can be adjusted.

Figure 13: Thermal simulations of the TW RF Photogun operating at 100 Hz (top) and 1000 Hz (bottom) with a peak input power of 82 MW.

4 Future plans and Conclusion

In the next months the two guns will be fabricated and tested. The test will consist in RF measurements at low power to calculate the coupling coefficient and reflections. Moreover bead pull measurements will be performed to calculate the field profile along the structures. This mechanical realization and full rf characterizations will be the subjects of the next delivery report D7.4: mechanical realization and low power rf tests of the two guns (M38). The setup of the high power test stand is also in progress at PSI and it will host the two guns that will be tested at high power. During the high power tests, breakdown rate measurements will be performed with cathode peak field above the 160 MV/m level. These final results will be reported in the final milestone MS29: high power rf tests of the two guns (M46).

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